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Beyond Technical Feasibility: Cross- National Stakeholder Perspectives on Energy Transitions

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Authors

Gregor Zens - researcher of the SPES Project, International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA)

Vanessa Gathecha - researcher of the SPES Project, Partnership for Economic Policy (PEP)

Marjorie Alain - researcher of the SPES Project, Partnership for Economic Policy (PEP)

Contributors and peer reviewers

András Gábos, TÁRKI; István György Tóth, TÁRKI; Levente András Koczóh, Green Policy Center; Camilla Sofia Grande, ASviS; Andrea Ferrannini University of Florence; Tiziano Distefano, University of Florence; Leonardo Paoli, University of Florence; Katja Reuter, Social Platform; Albert Ferrari, European University Institute; Jacopo Cammeo, European University Institute; Eric Berr, Bordeaux School of Economics; André Meunié, Bordeaux School of Economics; Eric Rougier, Bordeaux School of Economics; Adeola Adenikinju, PEP; Vaqar Ahmed, PEP; Stephen Wainaina, PEP.

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	5
2. Methodological and Technical Details on Stakeholder Interactions	7
a. France.....	7
b. Hungary	7
c. Italy	8
d. Brussels / European Union	8
e. Pakistan.....	8
f. Nigeria	9
g. Kenya.....	9
3. Stakeholder Perspectives on Barriers to the Energy Transition.....	11
3.1. Social Acceptance & Behaviour.....	11
3.2. Economic & Financial Costs	13
3.3. Governance & Policy Coherence	14
3.4. Political Power & Vested Interests.....	16
3.5. Regulatory & Administrative Barriers.....	17
3.6. Technology & Infrastructure Constraints	18
3.7. Workforce & Skills Gaps.....	19
3.8. Industrial & Supply Chain Bottlenecks	19
3.9. Synthesis and Interconnections	20
4. Discussion and Concluding remarks	22
References.....	24

Abstract

We synthesize findings from stakeholder consultations conducted across seven case studies (France, Hungary, Italy, Kenya, Nigeria, Pakistan, and at the EU level) to identify implementation barriers for energy transitions that extend beyond technical feasibility. Through workshops and interviews engaging over 100 stakeholders from government, industry, civil society, and research institutions, we document challenges that are often underrepresented or operationalized only partially in quantitative energy scenarios. Despite the diverse geographical, institutional, and developmental contexts represented, stakeholders demonstrated substantial convergence on eight core barrier categories: social acceptance and behavior, economic and financial costs, governance and policy coherence, political power and vested interests, regulatory and administrative barriers, technology and infrastructure constraints, workforce and skills gaps, and industrial and supply chain bottlenecks. These barriers often operate as interconnected challenges—for instance, high upfront costs for clean technologies may undermine social acceptance among lower-income populations. The findings suggest that practitioners possess a sophisticated understanding of systemic implementation dynamics that formal models currently often underrepresent, and highlight the need to integrate social, political, and institutional factors into energy transition scenarios. Without accounting for these constraints, technically coherent transition pathways may prove difficult to implement, potentially misleading policymakers and eroding public confidence in the feasibility of sustainable energy futures.

1. Introduction

The transition from fossil fuel-based energy systems to renewable and sustainable alternatives has become a central imperative for addressing climate change and achieving sustainable development objectives. This energy transition represents a complex socio-technical transformation requiring coordinated action across multiple sectors and governance levels, with implications that often extend beyond technical system changes to encompass fundamental questions of societal organization and development pathways.

Energy transitions involve multiple interconnected dimensions—technological innovation, economic restructuring, environmental protection, social equity, and governance systems—making them inherently complex processes that require comprehensive analytical approaches.¹ Scenarios have emerged as essential tools for navigating the intricacies of energy transitions by providing plausible future outlooks that guide sustainability transformations through model-based pathways (Wiek et al., 2006; Weyant et al., 1995; Weyant, 2017; Hare et al., 2018). However, classical scenario literature exhibits important limitations in capturing the full complexity of these transitions. While recent synthesis reports emphasize the importance of social, cultural, and political developments (see, for example, Chapter 5 of the WG3 contribution to the IPCC AR6 report; Creutzig et al., 2022), these dimensions often remain weakly integrated in energy transition scenarios (Zens et al., 2024). This underrepresentation of sociopolitical factors—including political resistance, social opposition, governance failures, institutional barriers, and public trust dynamics—risks producing scenarios that, while technically coherent, insufficiently account for real-world implementation challenges (Smith & Mayer, 2018; Cologna & Siegrist, 2020; Sovacool, 2021).

While existing conceptual work has recognized the importance of socio-political dynamics in energy transitions (Geels, 2002; Meadowcroft, 2009; Turnheim et al., 2015; Cherp et al., 2018; Köhler et al., 2019; Cologna and Siegrist, 2020), cross-national syntheses of stakeholder perceptions remain scarce. Our study addresses this gap through a structured stakeholder engagement approach.² Through consultations with more than 100 stakeholders across France, Hungary, Italy, Kenya, Nigeria, Pakistan, and the EU level, we document perspectives on implementation barriers that extend beyond traditional scenario dimensions. These consultations capture insights on social impacts, governance challenges, financial constraints, and political obstacles that stakeholders identify as important for transition success. Our multi-country approach reflects the need to understand sustainability challenges across diverse development contexts, recognizing that transition pathways must be adapted to local conditions while addressing global imperatives.

The primary objective of these stakeholder engagements is to identify and synthesize cross-cutting barriers that emerged from these diverse consultations. We view this stakeholder-informed barrier identification as essential for developing more realistic and implementable future scenarios that incorporate the complex social, political, and institutional mechanisms currently often underrepresented in transition feasibility assessments. Our analysis contributes to transition studies

¹ This research is conducted within the SPES (Sustainability Performances, Evidence and Scenarios) project, a Horizon Europe initiative (2022-2026) that develops innovative approaches to measuring and analyzing sustainable human development. The SPES framework identifies energy as a cross-cutting policy field across five analytical pillars: productivity, equity, environmental sustainability, participation & empowerment, and human security. See Biggeri et al. (2023) and <https://www.sustainabilityperformances.eu/> for more information.

² This stakeholder-focused analysis complements other SPES research examining bottom-up citizen perspectives on environmental sustainability across different global contexts; compare Dokken et al. (2025).

literature, particularly the multi-level perspective on socio-technical transitions (Geels, 2002) and frameworks focusing on the politics of transitions (Meadowcroft, 2009). Empirically documenting how implementation barriers manifest across diverse national contexts further contributes to advancing politically-informed transition analysis (Köhler et al., 2019).

Despite originating from diverse institutional, geographical, and sectoral backgrounds, stakeholders demonstrated notable convergence on several fundamental barrier categories—including social opposition, governance failures, financial constraints, and technological bottlenecks. This convergence suggests these barriers may represent systematic challenges that should be addressed in credible transition strategies, reinforcing the need for scenarios that fully integrate social and political dimensions alongside technical pathways.

The remainder of this study is structured as follows. Section 2 details the methodological approach and technical aspects of the stakeholder engagements. Section 3 synthesizes the primary stakeholder insights regarding implementation barriers across different thematic blocks. Section 4 concludes with discussion of implications for future scenario development and priority areas for future research.

2. Methodological and Technical Details on Stakeholder Interactions

In total, seven stakeholder consultations were conducted across three continents. These consultations spanned the European Union (France, Hungary, Italy, and Brussels for EU-level perspectives), Africa (Kenya and Nigeria), and Asia (Pakistan), representing diverse energy systems, political structures, and development contexts. The implementation approach varied according to local needs and constraints, ranging from individual 90-minute interviews to full-day workshops with over 20 participants, utilizing in-person, online, and hybrid formats. Conducted between November 2024 and March 2025 in Europe and throughout 2024 in Africa and Asia, these consultations engaged over 100 stakeholders from diverse institutional backgrounds—including government ministers, EU policymakers, environmental NGOs, labor unions, energy companies, industry associations, research institutions, think tanks, and civil society organizations. Discussions focused on scenario feasibility, energy efficiency, renewable deployment, just transition policies, and the social impacts, governance challenges, financial constraints, and political obstacles affecting energy transitions. Through this comprehensive engagement process, both context-specific barriers and universal challenges emerged across the different regions. Details on each of these stakeholder interactions, including technical information, participant backgrounds, and specific discussion topics, are provided in the subsections below.

a. France

The French case study was led by the University of Bordeaux and conducted through individual 90-minute interviews between November 2024 and February 2025. The research engaged 12 high-profile stakeholders representing four distinct categories of energy transition actors in France. The interview format focused on the techno-economic and socio-political feasibility of France's energy transition, exploring enabling and hindering factors across five policy instruments: carbon prices, decarbonization of the energy mix, energy effectiveness, electrification of usages, and agriculture policies. Participants included policymakers (Ministry of Transition officials and a former Minister of Budget/current deputy), representatives from influential think tanks and expert organizations (Shift Project, Carbon 4, Negawatt, IDDRI), energy providers and service companies (EDF, RTE, France Renewables, Deepki), and major energy users from the industrial sector (Alstom, GERPISA).

b. Hungary

The social research institute TÁRKI organized the Hungarian workshop together with the Green Policy Center on January 23rd, 2025, in Budapest. The workshop followed a structured format beginning with an introductory presentation on background scenarios, followed by focused discussions on scenario feasibility, energy efficiency issues, and renewable energy production challenges. The event addressed critical topics including buildings, transport, district heating, electricity generation, grid development, and various renewable energy sources. Eight participants attended, representing key Hungarian energy sector stakeholders: government (Ministry for Energy), industry associations (Hungarian Solar Panel & Solar Collector Association), NGOs (Energiaklub, Hungarian Energy Efficiency Institute), private sector (Velux Magyarország Kft.), labor unions (Mining, Energy and Industrial Workers' Union, United Electricity Workers' Federation), and research

institutions (Regional Energy Research Centre). The workshop was moderated by researchers both from TÁRKI and the Green Policy Center.

c. Italy

The Italian case study comprised two workshops organized by ASviS and the University of Florence, both held at ASviS headquarters in Rome. The first workshop took place on February 19th, 2025 with 24 participants focusing on the social dimensions of energy transition and just transition policies. The second workshop, was held on March 24th, 2025 with 17 participants discussing clean technologies and renewable energy acceleration. Both workshops employed a face-to-face format with some online participation. Participants represented a broad spectrum of Italian stakeholders including environmental NGOs (Greenpeace, WWF, ECCO), labor unions (CGIL, CISL), business associations (CNA), energy companies (ENEL), research institutions and universities (Universities of Florence, Bologna, Bari, Milan, Padua, Calabria), foundations (Fondazione Sviluppo Sostenibile, Fondazione Ecosistemi, Fondazione Di Vittorio), and specialized organizations (Coordinamento FREE, MOTUS E, Forum Disuguaglianze Diversità).

d. Brussels / European Union

The European Union case study workshop was jointly organized by Social Platform and the European University Institute. The event took place on January 27th, 2025 at the Foundation for European Progressive Studies (FEPS) in Brussels, Belgium. The workshop employed a hybrid format with 22 participants, including 19 attending in person. The event featured an initial presentation and analysis of EU transition scenarios and instruments, and two focused discussion sessions examining institutional and civil society perspectives on carbon and energy prices and their social impacts. The participant group comprised 7 policymakers (including 2 Members of the European Parliament and 1 Head of Unit at the European Commission), 8 representatives from civil society organizations and think tanks, and 7 project partner organizers. Prior to the workshop, the organizers conducted expert interviews with four specialists - two energy experts and two carbon pricing experts, representing a mix of NGO/consulting backgrounds and academia, with geographic diversity from Western, Southern, and Eastern Europe.

e. Pakistan

The Pakistan case study employed a two-pronged approach: a series of key informant interviews (KIIs) and a multi-stakeholder workshop - both led by a senior research fellow of the Partnership for Economic Policy (PEP).

Between May 22nd and May 26th, 2024, KIIs were conducted with senior representatives from key public institutions, including the Ministry of Climate Change (Islamabad), National Energy Conservation Authority, Ministry of Petroleum, Ministry of Energy (Power Division), Ministry of Planning & Development, and the Board of Investment and Trade. Additional interviews included experts from the Sustainable Development Policy Institute (SDPI), USAID, Sub-national Governance Program (Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Province), Center of Excellence on CPEC, University of Gujrat, NUST Energy Research, and various development partner organizations. These discussions provided insights into institutional perspectives on sustainable energy transition policies and implementation challenges.

On November 7th, 2024, a stakeholder workshop was organized to support cross-sectoral dialogue amongst key actors influencing energy policy in Pakistan - including government agencies, academic institutions, think tanks, development partners, business associations, and media. Key institutional representation included the Ministry of Climate Change, Ministry of Petroleum, and the National Energy Conservation Authority. Additional participants came from the Prime Minister's Office, the Government of Sindh (Finance Department), the Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, the Pakistan Institute of Development Economics, Rawalpindi Chamber of Commerce and Industries, KPMG Pakistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Provincial Services Academy, Center for Private Sector Engagement, TMA Swabi, UK FCDO, and several universities and regulatory bodies such as the Competition Commission of Pakistan, Oil and Gas Regulatory Authority, and PEL Petroleum Exploration.

Notable contributions were also made by the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) Board of Investment, Centre of Excellence on CPEC, and the Ministry of Planning and Development (Islamabad). While non-government stakeholders were selected for their relevance to Pakistan's sustainability transition, these included gender-focused energy consultants, clean energy policy experts, and the Energy Sections of PIDE and SDPI. The SDPI Centre for Private Sector Engagement and the KP Board of Investment provided market and investment perspectives. The U.S. Embassy's Economic Section and the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Energy Department contributed regional and diplomatic insights. The Ministry of Planning and Development and the Centre of Excellence for CPEC supported the evaluation of energy scenario feasibility.

f. Nigeria

A high-level policy dialogue was organized and facilitated by a PEP-affiliated senior researcher in Abuja, Nigeria, on July 2nd, 2024. The event was hosted at the Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa (CSEA), but employed a hybrid format: 10 participants attended in person, while 7 joined virtually.

The convening was aimed at gathering expert and stakeholder perspectives on sustainability transition scenarios for Nigeria. The discussion focused on assessing the relevance and implications of global models and scenarios for sustainability transition (as described in Zens et al., 2024) in terms of economic impact, governance challenges, and viable national transition strategies in Nigeria's context.

The stakeholder group consisted of senior representatives from key federal and state government bodies, policy advisory institutions, and civil society organizations. Participating institutions included: Office of the Secretary to the Government of the Federation, Lagos State Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources, Oyo State Ministry of Budget & Economic Planning, Office of the Senior S.A to the President on Sustainable Development Goals (OSSAP-SDGs), Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Development, Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs and Poverty Alleviation, National Institute for Democratic and Legislative Studies (NILDS), Department of Climate Change, Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN), Centre for the Study of the Economies of Africa (CSEA), Ministry of Water Resources and Sanitation, Nigeria Institute of Social and Economic Research (NISER), Ministry of Communication, Innovation and Digital Economy and various Civil Society Organizations.

g. Kenya

In Kenya, a national stakeholder consultation meeting was organized and facilitated, again by a PEP collaborator, on July 24th, 2024 - with additional views shared on through a follow-up email exchange amongst the participants, up to September 12th, 2024. The meeting aimed to facilitate a structured

dialogue on country-specific energy transition pathways and the governance considerations involved in their implementation. As in Nigeria, the discussion also focused on the relevance and implications of global models and policy instruments to support energy transition in the context of Kenya.

A total of 10 key policymakers represented a range of institutions critical to energy and development planning. These included the Ministry of Transport, Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS), State Department of Economic Planning (at the National Treasury), Ministry of Energy, Ministry of Health, and the UN Resident Coordinator's Office. Academic perspectives were incorporated through participation from the University of Nairobi, and the Kenya Institute for Public Policy and Research Analysis (KIPPRA).

3. Stakeholder Perspectives on Barriers to the Energy Transition

Eight cross-cutting barrier categories emerged consistently across stakeholder consultations, despite the diverse geographical, institutional, and sectoral contexts represented:

1. Social Acceptance & Behaviour
2. Economic & Financial Costs
3. Governance & Policy Coherence
4. Political Power & Vested Interests
5. Regulatory & Administrative Barriers
6. Technology & Infrastructure Constraints
7. Workforce & Skills Gaps
8. Industrial & Supply Chain Bottlenecks

These categories emerged through a systematic analysis of the stakeholder consultation materials. The categorization process involved three authors independently reviewing the workshop materials and stakeholder quotes provided by implementing partners. Each author developed initial thematic categories through inductive coding, which were then compared and consolidated through iterative discussion to arrive at the eight final barrier categories presented here. This collaborative approach helped ensure consistency while allowing for emergent themes to be captured across the workshop contexts.

While these eight categories provide a useful framework for analysis, they are not entirely discrete—considerable overlap exists between them, particularly among the subcategories discussed in the following subsections. These interconnections reflect the complex, multifaceted nature of the barriers themselves, which often interact and compound one another. We address this in a broader synthesis at the end of this section, where we also briefly examine how the eight categories may influence each other.

The following analysis presents the eight barriers in more detail. The topics are illustrated using direct quotes from the materials on stakeholder interactions provided by each of the implementing workshop partners, based on transcripts, ex-post summaries or notes taken during the sessions.

3.1. Social Acceptance & Behaviour

Stakeholders highlighted that social resistance to energy transition policies represents a fundamental implementation barrier, with opposition particularly acute when policies require lifestyle changes or disproportionately burden low-income populations. Stakeholders also suggested that social acceptance is not merely about communication, but fundamentally about policy design that addresses distributional impacts.

Resistance to Lifestyle Changes. Stakeholders across multiple contexts emphasized how policies requiring behavioral adaptation may face significant public pushback:

- **Hungary:** ‘Expecting lifestyle-change like eating less meat has a political cost; people tend to resist in such topics (others agreed and mentioned the resistance of several lobby groups as well, like the food and oil industry).’
- **France:** ‘Energy sufficiency should not be seen as deprivation, but as a rational and beneficial choice.’
- **Italy:** ‘Loss of trust in expert opinions, due to the proliferation of competing sources of authority (e.g., social media). [...] The promotion of a narrative that emphasizes the positive effects of the transition is required’.

The Hungarian perspective explicitly links lifestyle change resistance to political costs, while French stakeholders attempt to reframe the narrative around sufficiency—suggesting an awareness of the communication challenges involved.

- **Kenya:** ‘Carbon taxes can only be implemented in the petroleum sector to reduce emissions but will have the effect of increasing pump prices. This is likely to be very unpopular with the general public and operators within the transport sector.’
- **Kenya:** ‘For the Public, the widespread perception is that they are subjected to: exorbitant cost of new electricity installations, exaggerated electricity bills, reluctance and unwarranted responses to power black outs in certain areas, unnecessary delays in responding to the customers’ needs and also uncaring attitude of staff when it comes to handling of clients’ issues.’
- **Nigeria:** ‘Nigerians are extremely reluctant to accept any carbon tax in the face of crippling economic challenges. The initial efforts by the government to eliminate fuel subsidies have generated significant pushback by economic agents who view the fuel subsidy removal as the source of the high inflation rate in the economy. To sell a carbon tax would be extremely difficult.’

Social Justice and Distributional Concerns. The intersection of climate policy with social inequality emerged as a critical flashpoint:

- **EU:** ‘The pushback, from the evidence in events like the Yellow Vest demonstrations in France, highlights the need to consider both social approval and economic factors when developing carbon pricing strategies.’
- **EU:** ‘Acceptability: Low acceptability of the decarbonisation technologies by low-income households, as perceived as too costly.’
- **France:** ‘Carbon pricing, while essential to guiding industrial and individual choices, remains politically sensitive, as illustrated by the Yellow Vest protests in 2018.’
- **Nigeria:** ‘The vast majority of participants see the call for transition away from fossil fuels as an obvious way to limit the development aspirations of Nigeria, given the country’s abundant fossil fuel resources... The overwhelming sentiment is that Nigeria must continue to use all its fossil fuel resources.’
- **Italy:** ‘Widespread skepticism and opposition among the population concerning the social impacts of environmental policies. [...] Bottom-up mobilization (e.g., the GKN case) is needed to complement top-down strategies and introduce elements of rupture with the current socioeconomic model (see also the cases of RECs and Civitavecchia). Indeed, [...] grassroots mobilizations and local initiatives play a fundamental role in advancing a Just Transition. [...]

Use of economic and social redistributive policies and tools can make the transition socially acceptable.’

Stakeholders expressed resistance to carbon taxes and subsidy reforms due to economic hardship and distrust. They also mentioned potential issues related to low public awareness and technical understanding of renewable energy, especially solar, and limited appreciation of its economic benefits:

- **Nigeria:** ‘Communities / society (especially in the rural areas) also consider solar solutions as stop gap measures as they wait for the real solution of being connected to the electric power from the national grid.’
- **Pakistan:** ‘One of the main challenges was the lack of awareness and understanding of the economic benefits of green energy among stakeholders.’

3.2. Economic & Financial Costs

The transition is characterized by a two-fold financial constraint that was consistently emphasized across stakeholder consultations: potentially large underinvestment in infrastructure and system-wide capabilities, coupled with significant financial barriers faced by individual economic actors (households and enterprises):

Household-Level Financial Barriers. Stakeholders consistently highlighted how upfront costs create insurmountable barriers for many households:

- **Hungary:** ‘The financial investment needed for a renovation could be higher than the market value of the whole house. Pensioners are not likely to get into debt, and some of them live in oversized houses after their kids grow up.’
- **EU:** ‘High upfront costs for EVs and renovations (e.g., 15–18 months of median salary for EV) de facto prohibit households from accessing the benefits.’
- **France:** ‘Electric vehicles are still more expensive than combustion cars (even though costs are decreasing). Installing a heat pump costs between €10,000 and €15,000, an expense that is difficult for some households to afford.’
- **Pakistan:** ‘High upfront costs are a major hurdle, making solar and other renewable technologies largely inaccessible for households and small businesses.’
- **Italy:** ‘High energy costs for households and businesses, due to the predominant role of gas in the energy mix. [...] A heavy burden is placed on consumers (e.g., through the purchase of electric vehicles), who are not supported by adequate incentives. High energy costs reflected in household bills.’

The Hungarian example particularly illustrates how demographic factors (aging populations) can intersect with economic barriers to create complex implementation challenges. Further examples of potential interactions between various identified challenges are discussed at the end of this section.

System-Level Investment Gaps. Beyond individual costs, stakeholders identified potentially large macro-level funding needs and shortfalls:

- **EU:** ‘€65 billion SCF [Social Climate Fund] is clearly insufficient.’

- **Hungary:** ‘Renovating them [note: residential buildings with high energy-saving potential - so-called ‘Kádár-kocka’ buildings, which are abundant in Hungary] would be a ‘low-hanging fruit’. According to a study from 2023, an investment of 7 million HUF could create 63% energy consumption reduction and could be profitable even without state aid.’
- **Nigeria:** ‘At the inception in 2021, the Nigeria ETP’s investment requirement was put at \$1.9 billion. With limited fiscal space, it is obvious that the plan would be difficult to implement.’
- **Pakistan:** ‘We need significant investments in renewable energy infrastructure’.
- **Pakistan:** ‘Events like the Russia-Ukraine crisis have caused disproportionate energy inflation, making it harder for countries like Pakistan to access the resources needed for a clean energy transition’
- **Kenya:** ‘The financial investment for transitioning to sustainable energy is expected to be substantial and the country does not have such financial outlays.’
- **Italy:** ‘Need for an industrial policy capable of promoting the electrification of consumption and directing investments toward key sectors of the transition. [...] Insufficient renewable and storage capacity to meet the decarbonization targets for 2030 and 2050: increased investment in renewable and storage capacity are needed. [...] Limited use of funds from the EU ETS system and, even pre-emptively, the Social Climate Fund to support the transition.’

While stakeholders recognize the long-term economic benefits of transition investments (as noted in the Hungarian renovation example), the gap between current funding levels and requirements apparently remains large.

3.3. Governance & Policy Coherence

Stakeholders repeatedly mentioned how fragmented, short-term, and contradictory policy approaches can significantly undermine transition effectiveness, creating uncertainty that deters investment and erodes public trust.

Policy Inconsistency and Contradiction. Multiple stakeholders emphasized how conflicting policies work at cross-purposes:

- **Hungary:** ‘National strategies are in contradiction to each other (e.g. the expected growth in industrial capacities makes climate transition much harder).’
- **France:** ‘France’s energy policy is often caught between conflicting priorities ... creating uncertainty for investors and slowing down the energy transition.’
- **Nigeria:** ‘The debate lies in the speed and how to finance the policy options to drive the appropriate energy mix, given the high rate of energy poverty and macroeconomic challenges facing the economy. Hence, energy security and energy equity rank much higher than issues.’
- **Kenya:** ‘The tariffs they charge the consumer (and therefore the profits) are determined by law. There is therefore no motivation whatsoever for the company (a monopoly) to achieve cost or operational efficiencies.’
- **Kenya:** ‘The resources allocated to R&D (either by the government or private sector) are very insignificant to have any meaningful impact on the economy.’

- **Italy:** ‘Lack of a legislative framework to support the climate targets and the adoption of renewable energy. The phase-out from fossil fuels is not clearly supported by the PNIEC.’

The Hungarian example demonstrates how sectoral policies (industrial growth) can directly contradict climate objectives, while France's experience suggests that such contradictions create investment uncertainty.

Implementation Failures and Reversals. Beyond contradictions, stakeholders identified active weakening of existing policies:

- **Hungary:** ‘Hungary repeatedly asked for derogation in the field of energy efficiency of new buildings.’
- **EU:** ‘Implementation is lagging behind and is being actively weakened/rolled back by some political stakeholders.’
- **EU:** ‘Lack of accountability between MS [Member States] and the EU on the implementation of ETS 2.’
- **Kenya:** ‘Although policy framework may be appropriate, other governance concerns are seen as the weakest link to getting it right.’
- **Kenya:** ‘In general, Kenya has made considerable strides in electrification, including growth in e-mobility. [...] The sector, however, is faced with many governance challenges despite being well funded by Government and development partners. The high transmission losses and poor energy infrastructure, coupled with poor governance issues, in general leads to huge challenges in the pace of overall electrification provision in the Kenyan economy.’
- **Nigeria:** ‘Some of the challenges include lack of funding to implement measures put in place in various policies and plans; implementation capacity at all levels of governance; and weak coordination among key stakeholders.’
- **Pakistan:** ‘Policy gaps, such as unclear net metering regulations and limited incentives, discourage wider adoption.’

Absence of Long-term Vision and Coordinated Action. The lack of strategic coherence and coordination between structures and sectors emerged as a fundamental governance challenge:

- **France:** ‘[a stakeholder] calls for a 'long-term vision' and criticizes the absence of a clear state strategy.’
- **EU:** ‘EU funding instruments require immediate simplification together with better coordination. The available resources are not sufficient, and implementation inefficiencies and instrument fragmentation prevent them from achieving their full potential.’
- **Nigeria:** ‘There is also a necessity for increased harmonization of efforts to ensure optimization of resources and align shared goals, particularly between and among the top echelons of the Presidency.’
- **Nigeria:** ‘Lawmakers, public servants, and National Assembly members must be constantly reminded through training, workshops, conferences, and advocacy of these sustainable energy transition-related policy implementation efforts to ensure streamlined activities and reduced policy conflicts.’

- **Kenya:** ‘The governance for such a transition [to sustainable energy] is also weak and will require multi-sectoral coordination.’
- **Italy:** ‘Lack of a clear governance vision to lead the transition, with significant decision-making power delegated to the regions. This has led to territorial conflicts and delays caused by local interests and administrative fragmentation. [...] Needed an urgent call by the Government to convene a national roundtable for dialogue, based on a participatory governance model and informed by the contents of the 2023 International Labour Conference Declaration on Just Transition.’

3.4. Political Power & Vested Interests

Organized opposition from incumbent industries and their political allies was discussed as actively obstructing transition policies, with agricultural and fossil fuel lobbies wielding particular influence.

Lobby Group Resistance. Stakeholders explicitly mentioned interest groups blocking progress:

- **Hungary:** ‘Others agreed and mentioned the resistance [note: for example, towards the promotion of life-style changes] of several lobby groups as well, like the food and oil industry.’
- **France:** ‘The taxation of methane and nitrous oxide has been systematically blocked by the FNSEA [France's main agricultural union].’
- **France:** ‘Large agricultural cooperatives are slowing down the transition to more sustainable models.’
- **Kenya:** ‘The (energy) sector is susceptible to cartel-like behavior. Example is the Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs) done between the government and the Independent Power Producers (IPPs) for diesel power production as back-up power, which are very expensive.’
- **Italy:** ‘Role of fossil fuel lobbies in slowing-down the transition towards renewable energies.’

Political Exploitation of Transition Resistance. Beyond industry lobbying, it was highlighted that political actors may exploit transition anxieties:

- **EU:** ‘Acceptability: Political resistance (especially far-right), weak public buy-in.’
- **EU:** ‘Political exploitation by the far-right.’
- **Italy:** ‘Opposition between environmental policies and social and economic issues, promoted by parties (especially the far-right) against the transition’

Particularly in the EU, stakeholders see the intersection of industry lobbying with populist political movements as a potential coalition against transition policies. This is sometimes viewed as going beyond technical disagreements to include political opposition that draws on public concerns about change.

3.5. Regulatory & Administrative Barriers

Stakeholders discussed how excessive bureaucracy and poorly designed regulations create implementation bottlenecks that particularly affect renewable energy deployment and building renovation.

Over-regulation and Contradictory Rules. Stakeholders noted how regulations can actively impede transition. These examples show how regulations can be not just burdensome but actively counterproductive:

- **Hungary:** 'There are too many administrative obstacles (for example, it is illegal to build solar PVs above car parks or to install balcony PVs).'
- **Hungary:** 'On one hand, renewable energy projects are over-regulated (too hard to get permission for feed-in to the grid, the permitting process for large-scale projects can take up to 2 years and they have to wait for around 5 more years to be able to enter).'
- **Nigeria:** 'There are multiple regulatory agencies in the energy space with overlapping responsibilities.'
- **Pakistan:** 'Fragmented policies and frequent shifts in the regulatory landscape have deterred investment in renewable energy.'
- **Pakistan:** 'We need to create an enabling environment for private sector participation'
- **Italy:** 'Simplification of bureaucratic procedures is needed to facilitate the access to funding and technologies'

Fragmented Support Systems. Stakeholders also highlighted how administrative complexity can negatively impact support mechanisms:

- **EU:** 'Fragmented funding landscape complicates access.'
- **EU:** 'Multiple funds and underused resources.'
- **France:** 'Public aid (MaPrimeRénov', Energy Savings Certificates) is poorly calibrated and sometimes ineffective. They often cover only part of the costs and are complex to access.'
- **France:** 'France lags in renewable energy deployment ... due to administrative hurdles and lack of political commitment.'

The 7-year total timeline for Hungarian renewable projects (2 years permitting + 5 years waiting) exemplifies how administrative barriers can counteract policy ambitions. The underuse of available funds due to complexity suggests that simplification could unlock existing resources without requiring additional funding.

3.6. Technology & Infrastructure Constraints

Stakeholder discussions consistently highlighted how aging grid infrastructure and immature storage technologies create hard technical limits on transition speed, with grid constraints emerging as particularly acute bottlenecks. This perspective suggests a fundamental mismatch between existing infrastructure design philosophy and future system requirements.

Grid Infrastructure Limitations. Stakeholders consistently identified electricity grid inadequacy:

- **Hungary:** 'The Hungarian electricity grid is not fit for the new circumstances.'
- **France:** 'The current grid was designed for centralized production (nuclear, hydropower), while renewables require decentralized generation.'
- **Pakistan:** 'The weak national grid remains a bottleneck in integrating renewable energy.'
- **Kenya:** 'Electricity production is not adequate to satisfy the demands of the population. [...] Challenges are also in the transmission of electric power, which is inefficient with significant power losses. [...] The country has, however, a clear path of energy mix and has invested heavily on renewable energy, thus the energy mix has been growing.'
- **Italy:** 'Insufficient renewable and storage capacity to meet the decarbonization targets for 2030 and 2050.'

Technology Maturity Gaps. It was mentioned how key technologies remain insufficiently developed:

- **Hungary:** 'Technology is also a barrier, e.g. carbon capture, utilisation and storage (CCUS), which is not yet market ready (especially the 'utilisation' part).'
- **France:** 'Storage technologies exist but are not yet fully effective, especially for seasonal balancing.'
- **EU:** 'Collapse in heat pump market (-27% in 2023), slow wind deployment.'
- **Kenya:** 'The existence of adequate charging stations for EVs is currently quite limited.'
- **Italy:** 'The NECP places significant emphasis on new technologies (e.g., nuclear, green hydrogen), which are still too premature to play a major role in the transition. Gas continues to hold an overly prominent role. [...] Underutilization of existing sources and technologies that could reduce the impact of hard-to-abate sectors (e.g., biogas, electric arc steelmaking).'

Market and Supply Dependencies. Stakeholders discussed how infrastructure constraints can interact with market dynamics:

- **EU:** 'Dependence on imports and market dynamics limits EU control.'
- **Kenya:** [Energy efficiency] 'The cost of production, low infrastructure and transmission losses leads to acute challenges in the sector thereby complicating the energy efficiency parameters.'
- **Kenya:** 'On distribution, the problem is power losses especially in the distribution lines which could be as high as 20%. These losses and high tariffs, especially from thermal energy are passed over to the consumer as expensive energy.'

3.7. Workforce & Skills Gaps

A key discussion point in several consultations was the acute shortages of skilled workers which can create a fundamental capacity constraint on transition implementation:

- **Pakistan:** ‘Technology transfer and capacity building are also crucial. We need to equip our workforce with the skills needed for the green economy.’
- **Kenya:** ‘A transition to EVs and other modes of electric transportation will require capacity building on the expertise of handling the new technology.’
- **Italy:** ‘Focus on active labour policies that do not adequately consider potential challenges related to upskilling, reskilling, or worker relocation. Need to design active and passive policies aimed at protecting workers who are at risk of exclusion during the transition process.’
- **Hungary:** ‘Lack of skilled workforce as workers migrate towards the West – more harmonised payments are needed in the EU.’

Construction Sector Bottlenecks. In the EU countries, capacity constraints were discussed as particularly salient in the construction and renovation sectors, where stakeholders identified critical workforce shortages:

- **Hungary:** ‘The greatest bottlenecks in a faster increase of energy efficiency are ... the capacities of the building contractors.’
- **France:** ‘The renovation sector lacks trained craftsmen for comprehensive and efficient renovations.’
- **France:** ‘A lack of qualified labor is highlighted by several stakeholders, with the renovation sector unable to meet demand.’

The workforce constraint appears particularly binding in the building renovation sector—a critical component of most transition strategies. The Hungarian observation about east-west migration suggests that workforce gaps in some regions may be structural, requiring EU-level coordination.

3.8. Industrial & Supply Chain Bottlenecks

With respect to industrial organization, stakeholders discussed how limited domestic manufacturing capacity for clean technologies and complex international supply chains can create dependencies that constrain transition autonomy and speed.

Supply Chain Vulnerabilities. Stakeholders highlighted material and equipment dependencies:

- **Hungary:** ‘Green transition needs a lot of raw material and equipment which is imported from abroad, causing high GHG emissions in the maritime sector.’
- **Hungary:** ‘It happened before that a power plant switched to solid biomass and had to close in a few years due to a lack of feedstock.’

- **Pakistan:** 'Participants noted Pakistan's dependence on imported technologies and the lack of investment in local research and development.'
- **Italy:** 'Dependence on raw materials and gas, usually imported from abroad, with national energy supply policies still aligned with a Business-as-Usual scenario.'

The biomass example illustrates how transition plans can fail due to poor supply chain assumptions underlying the policy decisions.

Loss of Domestic Industrial Capacity. Strategic industrial weaknesses compound supply challenges:

- **France:** 'France's wind industry, initially developed for export, is now entirely foreign-owned.'
- **France:** 'France imports 44% of its total energy needs, and nearly 99% of its oil consumption relies on foreign supplies.'

The French wind industry example demonstrates how early technological leadership can be undermined without sustained policy support. Supply chain vulnerabilities extend beyond raw materials to industrial capacity and control, raising further questions about transition resilience and energy security.

3.9. Synthesis and Interconnections

Table 1 summarizes the eight cross-cutting barrier categories and their respective subheaders (as detailed in Sections 3.1–3.8) that were identified through the stakeholder interactions. For clarity, the second column groups these into four broader policy spheres, as the finer categorization contains unavoidable and blurred boundaries; using umbrella spheres can therefore be more practical when referring back to clusters of related issues in the text.

Importantly, the identified barrier categories do not operate in isolation, but constitute a complex web of *interconnected* challenges. For instance, social acceptance issues may intensify when economic costs burden groups in vulnerable situations. Governance failures amplify regulatory barriers and enable vested interests to obstruct progress. Technical constraints interact with workforce limitations to create implementation bottlenecks, while supply chain dependencies expose transitions to external shocks.

As a result, these barriers can likely not be addressed effectively in isolation. For instance, reducing household renovation costs requires not just financial support but also workforce development and regulatory simplification. Similarly, improving social acceptance may demand both equitable policy design and coherent long-term governance that builds public trust.

Table 1: Summary of energy transition barrier categories based on stakeholder engagements

Category	Broader context	Discussed Examples
Social acceptance & behaviour	Societal & political dynamics	Resistance to Lifestyle Changes; Social Justice and Distributional Concerns
Political power & vested interests	Societal & political dynamics	Lobby Group Resistance; Political Exploitation of Transition Resistance
Economic & financial costs	Economic & market structures	Household-Level Financial Barriers; System-Level Investment Gaps
Industrial & supply chain bottlenecks	Economic & market structures	Supply Chain Vulnerabilities; Loss of Domestic Industrial Capacity
Governance & policy coherence	Institutional & regulatory frameworks	Policy Inconsistency and Contradiction; Implementation Failures and Reversals; Absence of Long-term Vision and Coordinated Action
Regulatory & administrative barriers	Institutional & regulatory frameworks	Over-regulation and Contradictory Rules; Fragmented Support Systems
Technology & infrastructure constraints	Technological & capacity foundations	Grid Infrastructure Limitations; Technology Maturity Gaps; Market and Supply Dependencies
Workforce & skills gaps	Technological & capacity foundations	Construction Sector Bottlenecks

4. Discussion and Concluding remarks

This study suggests substantial convergence among stakeholders across diverse geographical and institutional contexts regarding the barriers to energy transition implementation. The main barriers identified by the stakeholders can be broadly summarized into the categories social acceptance & behaviour, economic & financial costs, governance & policy coherence, political power & vested interests, regulatory & administrative barriers, technology & infrastructure constraints, industrial & supply chain bottlenecks, and workforce & skills gaps. Despite representing different energy systems, political structures, and economic conditions—from Hungary's post-socialist transition challenges to France's nuclear-dominated energy landscape, from Nigeria's resource abundance to Kenya's development priorities—stakeholders identified several cross-cutting core barrier categories that transcend national boundaries and institutional differences.

Our findings contribute to transition studies by providing empirical evidence relevant to studying the 'implementation gap' between technically feasible scenarios and socio-politically viable pathways. This aligns with recent literature calling for greater integration of political economy perspectives in transition modeling (Cherp et al., 2018). Our results further illustrate the potential value of structured stakeholder consultation for identifying potential blind spots in contemporary quantitative scenario approaches. The convergence we observe suggests that expert practitioners often possess a sophisticated understanding of systemic implementation dynamics that formal models may not fully capture and that may be of relevance beyond the local contexts the specific stakeholders are operating in. Integrating this knowledge systematically into scenario development could significantly improve the policy relevance and implementation realism of future energy transition pathways. In this regard, incorporating social acceptance thresholds, governance capacity constraints, and political economy dynamics into scenario modeling represents a critical research frontier.

This suggests three focus areas for future research to facilitate bridging the gap between model-based scenarios and implementation reality. First, researchers could work on measuring and incorporating socio-political and institutional factors—such as social acceptance limits, governance capabilities, institutional preparedness, and vested interests—into quantitative modeling frameworks, whether existing or newly developed. Beyond measurement and quantification, a second research priority is on developing analytical frameworks that capture the cascading effects and feedback loops between barrier categories—for instance, workforce shortages can amplify regulatory delays, which in turn may increase costs and erode social acceptance, potentially creating self-reinforcing cycles of implementation failure. Understanding these interdependencies through systems analysis and empirical studies could enable modelers and policymakers to identify strategic intervention points where addressing one barrier could generate positive spillover effects across multiple challenge areas. Third, the temporal dynamics of implementation barriers requires further investigation. Some barriers may intensify as transitions accelerate (such as supply chain bottlenecks), while others may diminish with experience and learning (such as certain regulatory inefficiencies). Understanding these temporal dynamics is important for the design and understanding of plausible long-run transition pathways.

While our stakeholder consultations revealed consistent patterns across various contexts, several limitations of this study warrant acknowledgment. First, our workshops focused on European contexts plus selected African and South Asian countries, limiting the generalizability of findings to

other regions. Future research could expand geographical coverage to include additional political systems and development levels. Second, our stakeholder selection, while diverse, may have systematic biases toward actors already engaged in energy transition policy discussions. Including perspectives from actors outside the energy policy community – such as general business associations, or rural development organizations – could reveal additional barriers not captured in our current analysis. Similarly, while the observed stakeholder convergence on barrier categories is notable, it may partly reflect our sampling approach. Finally, it should be noted that our manual coding approach, while allowing for nuanced interpretation, lacks the inter-rater reliability measures common in more formal content analysis. Future studies could employ a larger number of coders and quantitative content analysis to validate our categorization.

To conclude, this report represents a first exploratory step toward developing plausible energy transition pathways that adequately represent political, social, and institutional implementation constraints. By systematically documenting the barriers that practitioners identify as significant, we provide a foundation for more realistic scenario modeling that can better inform policy design and transition planning. The eight barrier categories highlighted in our analysis merit consideration as important components of comprehensive energy transition assessments. Future outlooks that ignore these factors risk producing technically elegant but difficult-to-implement transition pathways that may mislead policymakers and undermine public confidence in transition feasibility.

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